

Produced result	Name of script(s) (all .py)
To obtain the hourly SLP and T2m values at Adventdalen, Danmarkshavn and the Polarstern. Executed on HPC Anunna.	post_make2D_bw
Calculates the RMSE, MAE and d-values for SLP and T2m in appendix. Values are calculated between the observations and the simulated values. The average values of those are then calculated manually. Executed in Spyder	time_series_adventdalen time_series_danmarkshavn mosaic_time_series
To create the hourly vertical profiles at Andoya, Bjornoya, Danmarkshavn, Ittoqqortoormiit, Jan Mayen, Polarstern and Ny-Alesund. Among the calculated variables are: pressure, geopotential height, temperature, potential temperature, relative humidity, specific humidity, wind speed, wind direction and boundary layer height. Executed on HPC Anunna.	post_make3D_bw
RMSE, MAE and d-value calculated between the observations and the simulated vertical profiles. Each script is run at all locations (except mosaic, because of other data format it needed its own script), and automatically loops through all the available observations. The RMSE, MAE and d-values are written to a separate text file: vertical_profiles_{variable}.txt. In which {variable} is substituted with one of the just mentioned variables. Executed in Spyder.	vertical_profile_temperature vertical_profile_potential_temperature.py vertical_profile_relative_humidity.py vertical_profile_specific_humidity.py vertical_profile_wind_direction vertical_profile_wind_speed mosaic_vertical_profile_temperature mosaic_vertical_profile_potential_temperature mosaic_vertical_profile_relative_humidity mosaic_vertical_profile_specific_humidity mosaic_vertical_profile_wind_direction mosaic_vertical_profile_wind_speed
Boxplots of RMSE, MAE and d-values of the vertical profiles of temperature, potential temperature, relative humidity, specific humidity, wind direction and wind speed. Uses the vertical_profiles_{variable}.txt files as input. Executed in Spyder	boxplots_vertical_profile_runs
Same as above, but then visualized per location. Uses the vertical_profiles_{variable}.txt files as input. Executed in Spyder.	boxplots_vertical_profile
Summarizes the d-value for all observations for all variables. Uses the vertical_profiles_{variable}.txt as input. Executed in Spyder.	d_boxplot
Spatial plots of cloud fraction. Executed on HPC.	post_wrf_surface1_clouds.py
Cloud mask from satellite.	satellite
Visualize the observed vertical profiles of potential temperature, relative humidity and specific humidity, together with the simulated boundary layer height. Executed using Spyder.	vertical_profile_potential_temperature_pblh vertical_profile_relative_humidity_pblh vertical_profile_specific_humidity_pblh mosaic_vertical_profile_potential_temperature_pblh mosaic_vertical_profile_relative_humidity_pblh mosaic_vertical_profile_specific_humidity_pblh

Plot observed vertical profile of potential temperature and simulated boundary layer height for the five runs (from the different configurations). Also used to compare the boundary layer heights between the base run and experiment SIC-&SST++ Executed using Spyder.	ny_pblh_vertical_profile
Spatial plot of boundary layer height. Executed on HPC.	post_wrf_surface1_pbl
Compare the latent, sensible and summed sensible and latent heat flux at the surface between the base run and experiment SIC-&SST++. Executed on HPC.	post_wrf_surface_compare_LH post_wrf_surface_compare_HF post_wrf_surface_compare_LH_HF
Visualize the vertical bulk shear (0-1 km). Executed on HPC.	post_wrf_shear
Calculated the hourly area which was considered to be PL. Resulted in a text file: filtered_pl_area_D2.csv Executed on HPC.	post_wrf_pl_area_total
Visualized the PL area as a timeseries and also performed the Wilcoxon signed rank test. Executed using Spyder	wilcoxon_pl_area
Calculated the hourly 90th percentile threshold for 10 m wind speed, inside the PL area. It also calculated the hourly average 10 m wind speed of the top 10%. Output is a file: percentile_90_pl_windspeed_D2.csv Executed on HPC.	post_wrf_percentile_pl
Visualized the timeseries of the 90th percentile threshold for 10 m wind speed inside the PL area. Executed using Spyder.	percentile_pl_intensity
Visualized the new PL index as proposed by Meyer et al. (2021). Executed on HPC.	post_wrf_surface1_new_pl_index
Visualized the cross section of potential vorticity Executed on HPC.	post_wrf_crossSection_pvo
Calculated the surface area of the MCAO ($M > 0$, as proposed by Dahlke et al. (2022)). Resulted in files per run, which were manually added together into: percentages_CAO_index.xlsx The average increases between the experiments and the base run were calculated manually as well. Also the maximum M and mean M were calculated manually. Executed on HPC and manually using Excel.	post_wrf_CAO_total
Performs the Wilcoxon signed rank test. Executed in Spyder.	wilcoxon_cao_area
To visualize the mean difference between M values between the base run and the experiments. Executed on HPC.	post_wrf_compare_mmean
To visualize the mean difference between Mp values between the base run and the experiments. Executed on HPC.	post_wrf_compare_mp
Calculates the mean difference in Mp between the base run and the experiments. Executed using Spyder.	domain_mean_mp